

A kinetic study for the photo-Persulfate degradation of a highly chlorinate pesticide, lindane, involving LVRPA.

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Conte, Leandro^{1,2}; Legnettino, Giuseppe¹; Santos, Aurora.¹ (1) Department of Chem. Eng. and Mat., Faculty of Chemical Sciences, Complutense University of Madrid, Madrid, Spain. (2) Instituto de Desarrollo Tecnológico para la Industria Química (INTEC) and, Universidad Nacional del Litoral (UNL), Santa Fe, Argentina.

A theoretical and experimental study for an innovative photo-Persulfate process proposed for the degradation of Lindane (γ -HCH) in water is presented. A kinetic model derived from a reaction mechanism is suggested using the ferrioxalate complex as iron source for conditions of neutral pH. The kinetic model will be employed to predict the concentrations of γ -HCHs, Persulfate (PS) and oxalate (Ox) in a flat plate laboratory reactor irradiated with a solar simulator. Here, the radiation field inside the reactor was considered through the Local Volumetric Rate of Photon Absorption (LVRPA). Two types of incident irradiation levels were tested by different combinations of attenuation filters. The effects of the iron (Fe) and oxidant concentration (PS), and the reaction temperature (T) on the degradation process were also investigated.

Introduction

Lindane (organochlorine pesticide), was intensely used on a worldwide scale during the second half of the 20th century. The inefficient production of this pesticide generated large volumes of the other HCHs isomers (mainly α , β - and δ -HCH, without insecticidal properties) which were inappropriately dumped during decades in the vicinity of the production site. In addition, due to their high toxicity and persistence in the environment, the EPA has classified HCHs as possible human carcinogens. Moreover, the isomers α -HCH, β -HCH and γ -HCH have been included in the list by the Stockholm Convention. In the last decade, a remarkable experimental effort has been made to better understand the Advanced Oxidation Process (AOPs) photo-activated (photo-Fenton, photocatalysis, etc) [1]. Concerning photo-AOPs kinetics modelling, different model-based approaches have been proposed to describe the process. However, many of these models are only an approximation to the understanding of the phenomenon since they do not satisfactorily consider the interactions of radiation in the reacting medium.

Hence, the present study aims to develop a kinetic model (derived from a reaction sequence) that can describe an innovative photo-Persulfate process proposed for the Lindane (γ -HCH) degradation. This considering the effect of the Local Volumetric Rate of Photon Absorption (LVRPA) in the system, using the ferrioxalate complex as an iron source.

The kinetic model was employed to predict the concentrations of γ -HCH, Persulfate (PS), and oxalate (Ox) in a flat plate laboratory reactor irradiated with a solar simulator. The effects of the

iron and PS concentration, the reaction temperature (T), and the radiation level (Rad) on the photo-Persulfate process were also investigated.

Materials and Methods

The general methodology consists of an experimental part and a modelling part including model fitting (parameter estimation). The experimental step provides the data that will be used in the final optimisation step, so to estimate the kinetic parameters of the proposed model (see Graphical Abstract). Experimental studies were performed in batch mode with recirculation, in a laboratory system consisting in a glass reservoir (2 L) and a double jacket flat plate photo-reactor equipped with a solar simulator (Oriel, model 67005) and with an irradiated volume of 0.54 L. Initial concentrations of PS and iron (Fe) were varied between 250 and 1500 mgL^{-1} , and between 3.5 and 10 mgL^{-1} , respectively, for a same value of the initial concentration of γ -HCH (saturation concentration, 9.5 mgL^{-1}) and for a total reaction time of 6.5 hr.

The modelling part starts by proposing a kinetic model shown in Table 1 (based on the assumptions by [2]). The degradation rate expressions of Lindane, oxidant agent (PS), and oxalate (Ox), can be written by using the matrix representation as indicated in eq. 1. The mass balances and the initial conditions are given by the set of first order, ordinary differential eqs. 2 and 3 (matrix notation).

Eq. 1 is solved to obtain the mathematical expressions of $R_i(x,t)$. To do this, the steady state approximation (SSA) may be applied for highly reactive radicals' species ($SO_4^{\cdot-}$).

$$R(x, t) = R^T(t) + R^{irr}(x, t) \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \mathbf{C}(t) = \mathbf{R}^T(t) + \frac{V_{irr}}{V} \varphi \left\langle \sum_{\lambda} e_{\lambda}^a(\underline{x}, t) \right\rangle_{V_{IRR}} \mathbf{\Gamma}(t) \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{C}^0 \quad t = 0 \quad (3)$$

The first term on the right-hand side of eq. 1 or 2, corresponds to the thermal reaction rate. For example, for PS it may be represented by eq. 4. The expression for de $SO_4^{\cdot-}$ radicals is given by eq. 5.

$$R_{PS}^T(t) = -C_{PS} \left(k_3 C_{SO_4^{\cdot-}} + k_1 C_{Fe^{(III)}(C_2O_4)_3^{3-}} + k_2 C_{Fe^{(II)}(C_2O_4)} \right) \quad (4)$$

$$C_{SO_4^{\cdot-}} = \left[\frac{k_1 C_{Fe^{(III)}(C_2O_4)_3^{3-}} C_{PS} + k_2 C_{Fe^{(II)}(C_2O_4)} C_{PS}}{k_3 C_{PS} + k_4 C_{\gamma-C_6H_6Cl_6} + k_5 C_{C_2O_4^{2-}}} \right] \quad (5)$$

On the other hand, the second term on the right-hand side of these eq. 1 and 2 corresponds to the i-component degradation by both the radiation activated and thermal reactions occurring inside the irradiated liquid volume (photo-Persulfate reaction). Here, it is necessary to know the value of the Local Volumetric Rate of Photon Absorption (LVRPA) at every point inside the reactor and then to compute the LVRPA averaged over the reactor volume ($\langle \sum_{\lambda} e_{\lambda}^a(\underline{x}, t) \rangle_{V_{IRR}}$).

To compute it, a one-dimensional radiation field model has been used [3]. Thus,

$$e_{\lambda}^a(\underline{x}, t) = \kappa_{\lambda}(\underline{x}, t) q_{w,\lambda} f_{\lambda} \exp[-\kappa_{T,\lambda}(\underline{x}, t) x] \quad (6)$$

Where $q_{w,\lambda}$ is the spectral net radiation flux at the reactor wall, f_{λ} the normalized spectral distribution of the lamp output power, $\kappa_{\lambda}(\underline{x}, t)$ the volumetric absorption coefficient of the reacting species, and $\kappa_{T,\lambda}(\underline{x}, t)$ the volumetric absorption coefficient of the medium. This allowed to calculate the $\langle \sum_{\lambda} e_{\lambda}^a(\underline{x}, t) \rangle_{V_{IRR}}$ as a function of $C_{Fe^{(III)}(C_2O_4)_3^{3-}}$

(this last was considered as the only absorbing specie for $\lambda > 300\text{nm}$) and is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 $\langle \sum_{\lambda} e_{\lambda}^a(\underline{x}, t) \rangle_{V_{IRR}}$ calculated as a function of iron concentration ($C_{Fe^{(III)}(C_2O_4)_3^{3-}}$) by the proposed radiation model. At present, the corresponding experimental tests are being finalized. Then, the kinetic parameters will be estimated by applying the nonlinear regression procedure of Newton Gauss-Marquardt.

Conclusions

Lindane could be successfully degraded using an innovate photo-Persulfate process. Ferrioxalate and a solar simulator as used iron and radiation source, respectively. Among the studied variables, it could be seen that the largest effect in Lindane conversion was due to Rad (the most significant term), followed by Fe, and finally the PS concentration.

References

- [1] C. Dominguez, A. Checa-Fernandez, A. Romero, A. Santos. J. Environ. Chem. Eng., 9 (2021), 105668
- [2] L. Conte, A. Schenone, O. Alfano. J. Environ. Manage., 170 (2016) 60-69
- [3] L. Conte, J. Farías, E. Albizzati, O. Alfano. Ind. Eng. Chem. Res., 51 (2012), 4181-41911.
- [4] H. Kusi, I. Peternel, S. Ukic, N. Koprivanac, T. Bolanca, S. Papic, A. Bozic. Chem. Eng. J., 172 (2011) 109-121.

Table 1 Reaction scheme of Lindane degradation

Nº	Reaction step	Kinetic parameter
0	$Fe^{(III)}(C_2O_4)_3^{3-} \xrightarrow{h\nu} Fe^{(II)}(C_2O_4) + CO_2 + 1.5C_2O_4^{2-}$	$\overline{\Phi}_{Fe^{(II)}(C_2O_4)} = 1.21 molE^{-1}$ (a) $\overline{\Phi}_{C_2O_4^{2-}} = 1.05 molE^{-1}$ (a)
1	$Fe^{(III)}(C_2O_4)_3^{3-} + S_2O_8^{2-} \rightarrow Fe^{(II)}(C_2O_4) + 2C_2O_4^{2-} + SO_4^{\cdot-} + SO_4^{2-}$	$k_1 = \exp \left[A + B \left(\frac{T - T_{ref}}{T} \right) \right]$ A and B (to be estimated).
2	$Fe^{(II)}(C_2O_4) + S_2O_8^{2-} + 2C_2O_4^{2-} \rightarrow Fe^{(III)}(C_2O_4)_3^{3-} + SO_4^{\cdot-} + SO_4^{2-}$	k_2 (to be estimated)
3	$S_2O_8^{2-} + SO_4^{\cdot-} \rightarrow S_2O_8^{\cdot-} + SO_4^{2-}$	k_3 (to be estimated)
4	$\gamma - C_6H_6Cl_6 + SO_4^{\cdot-} \rightarrow \text{Products}$	$k_4 = 8.95 \times 10^6 M^{-1} s^{-1}$ (b)
5	$C_2O_4^{2-} + SO_4^{\cdot-} \rightarrow 2CO_2 + SO_4^{2-}$	k_6 (to be estimated)

A and B, Arrhenius parameters, Tref=298 °K. (a) Values taken from Conte et al., 2016. (b) Values taken from Kusic et al., 2011.

Keywords: Kinetic Model, Local Volumetric Rate of Photon Absorption, photo-Persulfate, Lindane, Solar Simulator

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